

Data Storage

Tip 1: Follow the 3-2-1 Principle

3
**Digital
Copies**

2
**Storage
Mediums**

1
**Off-Site
Location**

Tip 2: Use University Storage Solutions

Service	Storage Space	Collaborative Features	Cost	Availability
Personal Online Storage Space (Z: Drive)	10 GB; expandable with justification	None	Free	Immediate
u:cloud	50 GB	Between employees and students; Outside users can upload and download	Free	Immediate
u:cloud pro	250 GB; expandable with justification	Between employees and students; Outside users can upload and download	EUR 0.03 per GB/year	Request Required
Share	Unlimited	Between employees and students; u:account available for guests	EUR 0.03 per GB/year	Request Required
One Drive by Microsoft	50 GB	Internal and external sharing; Non-university users can edit files	Free	Immediate
Gitlab	Unlimited; code and documentation only	Permissions and licensing options available	Free	Request Required

RDM Homepage

How to Reach the RDM Team

Anyone at univie can reach-out to the RDM team for help. You can reach us at rdm@univie.ac.at or find our webpage at rdm.univie.ac.at.